

Post-Infectious Cerebellitis in Pediatric Age: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Ataxia is defined as impaired coordination of voluntary motor activity. Clinical features include broad-based gait, tremor, truncal instability, dysarthria, and nystagmus. In most children, gait disturbance is the predominant symptom; However, cerebellar dysfunction may also manifest as fine motor impairment or tremor. Post-infectious cerebellitis is a rare but important cause of acute ataxia in pediatrics.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 10-year-old male who presented to the pediatric emergency department with a 5-day history of acute gastroenteritis, showing moderate dehydration, oral intolerance, persistent vomiting, asthenia, and adynamia. Twelve days before admission, he had a respiratory infection with fever, treated with cefotaxime for 7 days. Neurological examination revealed dysarthria, horizontal nystagmus, mildly decreased tone, dysdiadochokinesia, dysmetria, truncal and lateropulsion gait ataxia, impaired tandem gait, and intention tremor. Pediatric neurology evaluation confirmed the diagnosis of post-infectious cerebellitis, with a pancerebellar syndrome.

Management and Outcome: Systemic corticosteroid therapy was initiated, leading to clinical improvement and remission of neurological symptoms.

Conclusion: Post infectious cerebellitis should be considered in pediatric patients presenting with acute ataxia and a recent infectious history. Early recognition and appropriate management are crucial to ensure favorable outcomes and avoid unnecessary interventions.

KEYWORDS: Cerebellitis, Ataxia, Dysarthria, Nystagmus.

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INTRODUCTION

Ataxia is characterized by impaired coordination of motor activity. The main symptoms include wide-based gait, tremor, truncal instability, dysarthria, and nystagmus. These symptoms are primarily due to cerebellar dysfunction secondary to involvement of its afferent and efferent pathways, including the spinocerebellar, dendrorubrothalamic, and frontopontocerebellar pathways originating in the anterior part of the frontal lobe (Poretti et al., 2012). In acute cerebellar ataxia, meningeal signs, seizures, or fever are not usually present. It typically occurs in children under six years of age, although it can also affect older children and adolescents, representing between 35 and 60 percent of all cases of pediatric ataxia (Donald L. Gilbert, 2025).

A 2020 study presented a clinical series of 15 pediatric patients with a confirmed diagnosis of acute cerebellitis, ranging in age from 3 to 15 years (median 9.5 years). The most common initial symptoms were ataxia, vomiting, and headache, highlighting the inflammatory involvement of the cerebellum. Clinically, ataxia is characterized by loss of motor coordination, gait instability, tremor, and dysarthria—symptoms that significantly affect the patient's quality of life and require timely medical intervention. (Yildirim et al., 2020).

Regarding etiology, several infectious agents associated with the onset of acute cerebellitis were identified. These included *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, influenza A virus, cytomegalovirus, and varicella-zoster virus, each present in a separate case within the series. This etiological diversity suggests that cerebellitis can be triggered by multiple

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pathogens, which induce an aberrant immune response affecting cerebellar tissue (Yildirim et al., 2020). Consistent with this, other studies have reported that post-infectious inflammation occurs through autoimmune mechanisms that damage cerebellar structure and function after the initial resolution of the infection (Gómez Puche et al., n.d.).

A 2025 study also suggests that the pathogenic mechanisms underlying acute cerebellar ataxia are autoimmune in origin. In post-infectious cerebellar ataxia, the varicella-zoster virus is the most frequently implicated pathogen; however, numerous other infectious agents have been implicated, including coxsackievirus, echovirus, enteroviruses, Epstein-Barr virus, hepatitis A, herpes simplex virus 1, human herpesvirus 6, measles, mumps, parvovirus B19, *Borrelia burgdorferi*, SARS-CoV-2, malaria, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, and typhoid fever. (Donald L. Gilbert, 2025).

The two main causes of acute cerebellar ataxia in childhood are post-infectious and secondary to intoxication. Other etiologies to consider include head trauma, CNS infections, posterior fossa tumors, hereditary diseases, demyelinating processes, and immunological diseases (Anderson M, 2011). Acute cerebellar ataxia presents with a rapid onset and progression of symptoms, with onset occurring within hours or up to 1-2 days. In cases associated with a prodromal illness, ataxia usually appears within days to three weeks (Poretti et al., 2012).

The rate of symptom onset allows us to establish the diagnosis and prognosis of the disease. Poretti et al. (2012) compare a progressive, regular, and slow increase with bilateral and symmetrical involvement, suggesting a degenerative cause, as seen in hereditary spinocerebellar diseases. However, if the symptoms are unilateral, accompanied by headache, altered mental status, and cranial nerve involvement, it points toward a structural hemispheric cerebellar lesion. The main symptom in most patients with ataxia is gait disturbance; however, in other patients, cerebellar dysfunction may be limited to fine motor control problems or tremor. (Poretti et al., 2012)

The diagnostic evaluation for children presenting with ataxia includes a toxicological assessment. Ataxia can be observed with the ingestion of alcohol, benzodiazepines, or other anticonvulsants, or with exposure to environmental toxins such as mercury or lead. This underscores the importance of ruling out poisoning in pediatric patients with ataxia (Donald L. Gilbert, 2025). A 2012 study demonstrated that poisoning is the second most frequent cause of acute pediatric ataxia, accounting for approximately 30% of patients. It occurs in approximately 2% of children presenting to the emergency department with acute ingestion. It is most common in young children, with a second peak in adolescence.

Cerebellar symptoms are accompanied by a decreased level of consciousness of varying severity, seizures, and/or vomiting. (Poretti et al 2012) The differential diagnosis between acute cerebellitis and post-infectious ataxia is crucial due to the differences in management and prognosis. Post-

infectious ataxia typically presents with pure ataxia without signs of intracranial hypertension or significant neuroimaging abnormalities, while acute cerebellitis exhibits clinical and radiological signs of active inflammation and edema, requiring a more aggressive therapeutic approach (Yildirim et al., 2020). The presence of headache and vomiting along with ataxia should lead clinicians to suspect cerebellitis, necessitating immediate imaging studies to prevent severe complications (Yildirim et al., 2020; Gómez Puche et al., n.d.). From a neuroimaging perspective, brain magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) plays a crucial role in the diagnosis and monitoring of this condition.

In the cases studied by Yildirim et al. (2020), MRI showed bilateral and symmetrical hyperintense changes in the cerebellar cortex on T2-weighted sequences, accompanied by moderate edema. Furthermore, cerebellar tonsillar herniation was evident in 73.3% of patients, reflecting a significant increase in intracranial pressure with a risk of serious complications. The presence of obstructive hydrocephalus in 26.6% of cases also underscores the potential severity of this condition and the need for close monitoring. Studies by Donald L. Gilbert (2025) conclude that computed tomography has limited value, given the difficulty of obtaining images of the posterior fossa with this modality; its main function, in emergency situations, is to rule out conditions such as acute hemorrhage, mass effect, and hydrocephalus.

The treatment of acute cerebellitis is primarily based on the administration of intravenous and/or oral steroids to reduce cerebellar inflammation and edema. In some cases, intravenous immunoglobulin is added as immunomodulatory therapy. In the analyzed series, none of the patients required surgical intervention, reflecting the benefit of timely medical treatment (Yildirim et al., 2020). The rapid initiation of steroid treatment is associated with better functional outcomes and a reduction in long-term sequelae. However, the prognosis is not always favorable. At 12 months of follow-up, approximately one-third of the patients presented with persistent neurological sequelae, including residual ataxia, dysmetria, memory difficulties, and dysarthria, highlighting the prolonged impact of the disease and the importance of rigorous clinical follow-up (Yildirim et al., 2020). These aftereffects can affect the neurological development and quality of life of the pediatric patient, so rehabilitation and multidisciplinary care are an essential part of comprehensive management.

Up to 10 percent of children with acute cerebellar ataxia may experience some long-term neurological sequelae. Advanced age at diagnosis and associated Epstein-Barr virus infection appear to confer a worse prognosis (Donald L. Gilbert, 2025). Finally, post-infectious acute cerebellitis presents a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge in modern pediatrics. Early recognition, based on a detailed clinical analysis and the appropriate use of neuroimaging techniques, allows for differentiation from other causes of ataxia and helps avoid

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serious complications. Studies such as that by Yildirim et al. (2020) contribute to clinical knowledge and guide best practices for managing this condition, highlighting the need for clear and standardized protocols in secondary and tertiary pediatric units to optimize outcomes in this vulnerable population.

JUSTIFICATION

Post-infectious cerebellitis is a rare but highly relevant neurological condition in childhood, accounting for approximately 10–20% of cases of acute ataxia in children, with the highest incidence between 3 and 7 years of age. Its most frequent etiology is related to viral infections, including varicella-zoster virus (chickenpox), Epstein-Barr virus, influenza, enterovirus, and cytomegalovirus. The importance of studying this condition lies in the high prevalence of viral infections in the pediatric population, as well as the need for timely and targeted diagnosis, since it can mimic other serious neurological diseases, such as posterior fossa tumors, intoxications, trauma, and autoimmune diseases. Although most patients recover well, 20–25% may develop serious complications such as intracranial hypertension, neurological deterioration, or permanent sequelae. This clinical variability underscores the need to identify prognostic risk factors that allow us to differentiate patients with a benign course from those with a higher probability of complications and to establish timely treatment to prevent complications or neurological sequelae, as well as improve functional prognosis and quality of life in both the patient and the pediatric population.

General objective

- To describe the clinical-diagnostic and therapeutic approach to post-infectious cerebellitis in pediatric age, based on the presentation of a clinical case in a school patient, in order to highlight the importance of comprehensive neurological assessment and the timely use of complementary studies for effective and conservative management.

Specific objectives

- Identify the main clinical manifestations of acute ataxia and pancerebellar syndrome in the pediatric context.
- Analyze the differential diagnosis process performed, considering infectious, toxic, traumatic, metabolic, and tumoral causes.
- Document the laboratory, imaging, and diagnostic findings that supported the exclusion of other serious etiologies.
- Evaluate the clinical response to systemic steroid treatment in the presented case.
- Compare the patient's evolution with the evidence available in the literature on post-infectious cerebellitis and acute ataxia in children.

CLINICAL CASE PRESENTATION

We present the case of a 10-year-old male patient who presented to the pediatric emergency department with a clinical picture consistent with acute gastroenteritis of five days' duration, characterized by persistent vomiting, intolerance to oral intake, asthenia, adynamia, and signs of moderate dehydration upon admission. The patient's medical history includes both parents without chronic degenerative diseases, and he denies any family history of epilepsy or neurodevelopmental disorders. He is an only child. His personal history is notable for mild intermittent asthma, treated with short-acting beta2 agonists (SABAs) as rescue medication. He denies any history of hospitalization, surgery, head trauma, allergies, or recent vaccinations. He has adequate school performance, is in the fourth grade of primary school, has a complete vaccination schedule, lives in his own home made of durable materials, has no exposure to biomass, no zoonosis, and lives with three cats and one dog, all of which are dewormed and vaccinated. His diet and hygiene practices are adequate. As a relevant antecedent, 12 days prior to admission, the patient presented with a febrile respiratory illness of probable viral etiology, for which he was evaluated in a private consultation and started on antibiotic treatment with cefotaxime for seven days, completing the course without apparent complications. During his stay in the emergency department, the neurological examination revealed cerebellar signs: dysarthria, horizontal nystagmus, mildly decreased muscle tone, dysdiadochokinesia, dysmetria, gait ataxia with lateropulsion, unsteady tandem gait, and intention tremor. His level of consciousness was intact. Treatment was initiated with intravenous hydration and antiemetics, while a diagnostic approach was established for suspected acute cerebellar ataxia. Initial studies documented:

- Complete blood count without significant alterations.
- Serum electrolytes within normal parameters.
- Negative acute phase reactants.
- Elevated transaminases with elevated GGT.
- Lipid profile showing hypercholesterolemia.
- Renal function preserved and within values for age.

Secondary to elevated transaminases and a history of gastrointestinal symptoms such as vomiting and abdominal pain two weeks prior to the onset of neurological symptoms, an abdominal ultrasound was ordered. The ultrasound revealed hepatosplenomegaly and a solid-appearing nodular lesion adjacent to the head of the pancreas, the etiology of which is yet to be determined. Biochemical analysis showed pancreatic enzymes, LDH, and bilirubin levels within normal ranges. As per protocol, a pediatric gastroenterology consultation was requested, and a viral etiology was suspected, including respiratory viruses such as SARS-CoV-2 and influenza.

Initiation of immunoglobulin therapy is recommended if neurological symptoms do not improve with high-dose steroid treatment, along with prior serological testing using a

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viral panel that includes SARS-CoV-2, influenza, hepatitis A virus, Epstein-Barr virus, cytomegalovirus, echovirus, enterovirus, herpes simplex virus types 1 and 6, and parvovirus B19. It is important to note the patient's pre-existing conditions: obesity and dyslipidemia without steatosis confirmed by imaging at the time of admission. However, the patient is at high risk of developing NASH if nutritional interventions and dietary changes are not implemented.

The patient showed good progress, with resolution of gastrointestinal symptoms and improvement in hydration status after the start of treatment. No complications or target organ damage were observed. A good response to steroid bolus therapy was observed, and immunoglobulin therapy was not required. Follow-up with the gastroenterology service continued after discharge. A non-contrast computed tomography (CT) scan of the head was performed, which showed adequate differentiation between gray and white matter, normal basal ganglia, and preserved cisterns. No acute structural lesions were identified. Lumbar puncture revealed cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) with normal cytology and cytochemistry, without pleocytosis or elevated protein levels. The culture was negative. In addition, infectious causes were ruled out with negative PCR for hepatitis B and C viruses, as well as negative stool examination for parasites and stool culture. The patient was evaluated by the pediatric neurology service, which, based on the clinical course, neurological examination, exclusion of active infections, and absence of structural findings, made a diagnosis of post-infectious cerebellitis, confirming a pancerebellar syndrome. Based on this diagnostic impression, treatment was initiated with methylprednisolone succinate pulses, at a dose of 1 g daily (maximum dose 30 mg/kg/day) for 5 consecutive days, and a brain MRI was requested as a complementary study to evaluate possible underlying cerebellar abnormalities.

CLINICAL COURSE

Upon admission to the unit, the patient presented with moderate dehydration. Fluid replacement and antiemetic treatment with ondansetron were initiated due to persistent vomiting. A possible encephalitis was suspected after physical examination revealed persistent ataxic gait, intention tremor, dysarthria, and dysmetria. A non-contrast CT scan of the head was performed, ruling out structural abnormalities and signs of intracranial hypertension. A lumbar puncture was performed as part of the diagnostic protocol, with normal results. The patient was evaluated by the pediatric neurology service, which concluded that, based on the clinical presentation and the patient's prior infectious history, the diagnosis was pancerebellar syndrome and post-infectious cerebellitis. Treatment was initiated with steroids using methylprednisolone succinate pulses at a maximum dose of 1 gram every 24 hours, for a total of 5 boluses. A complete evaluation was ordered, including non-contrast and contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain and

neuraxis. The patient completed a 7-day hospital stay in our unit. Upon discharge, the patient showed good clinical progress with the established treatment, achieving remission of cerebellar symptoms. Follow-up continued in the pediatric neurology outpatient clinic, where good clinical progress and recovery from the disease were demonstrated, without associated complications or new neurological symptoms. The patient has now returned to normal activities without any limitations.

DISCUSSION

Acute cerebellar ataxia is an uncommon cause of pediatric consultation; however, it is important to understand its clinical presentation and its main etiology to ensure a comprehensive approach and early diagnosis, preventing complications and neurological sequelae, especially in presentations with high morbidity and mortality such as acute cerebellitis, opsoclonus-myoclonus syndrome, and cerebellar stroke. This knowledge is crucial for providing timely treatment. The diagnosis is primarily clinical, and other conditions must be ruled out, such as toxic ingestion (mainly benzodiazepines, alcohol, or other anticonvulsants), and infectious causes including meningitis, encephalitis, and labyrinthitis. Lumbar puncture is indicated in patients with fever, meningismus, seizures, or altered mental status to differentiate between an infectious process of the central nervous system and acute cerebellar ataxia. Post-infectious and autoimmune diseases can present with ataxia and include opsoclonus syndrome, myoclonus-ataxia, acute cerebellitis, autoimmune encephalitis, and acute disseminated encephalomyelitis. Structural abnormalities such as posterior fossa tumors or head trauma should be excluded, as well as metabolic and neurodegenerative diseases. In imaging studies, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is preferable to computed tomography (CT) due to its higher contrast resolution, greater sensitivity and specificity for visualizing brain lesions, and the absence of radiation. Acute cerebellar ataxia usually resolves without sequelae within two to three weeks of onset, with a mean duration of symptoms between 10 and 12 days. Rarely, symptoms persist for several weeks without improvement. Poor prognostic factors include advanced age at diagnosis and association with Epstein-Barr virus.

CONCLUSION

Understanding the primary etiology and differential diagnoses of acute cerebellar ataxia allows for a comprehensive and thorough diagnostic approach, ruling out pathologies with high morbidity and mortality and a risk of neurological sequelae. In general, cerebellar ataxia is self-limiting and responds well to established medical treatment. However, approximately 10% of patients experience long-term neurological sequelae. The presented case demonstrates a post-infectious cerebellar syndrome secondary to a respiratory infection of apparent viral origin in a school-aged

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child. Based on the clinical presentation and complementary studies, the diagnosis was established in a timely manner. The patient received pharmacological treatment with steroid pulses, responding well and showing good clinical progress. This highlights the importance of a proper diagnostic approach to avoid complications and neurological sequelae that can affect the patient's quality of life.

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